

Special Issue

Open Science in its many forms

Insights about Open Science development in Romania: a Funding Agency perspective

Discover how a main funder of competitive research is reshaping Romania's research landscape through Open Science. From leading national strategies to aligning with global initiatives, UEFISCDI pioneers innovative practices, fostering collaboration. Learn about their milestones, challenges, and vision for a future where Open Science and equitable research assessment drive scientific excellence.

What is the role of UEFISCDI, a funder of competitive research, in shaping Open Science in Romania?

The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development, and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI) in Romania is a prominent force in promoting Open Science. As Romania's primary funding organization for competitive research, UEFISCDI plays a dual role: funding research and advising policies. Additionally, UEFISCDI leads Romania's open

Photo by Alina Irimia

Bionote

Alina Irimia leads the Open Science (OS) projects at UEFISCDI and is an OS policy expert at the UNESCO Chair for Science and Innovation Policy at SNSPA-Bucharest. Over the past 8 years, she has collaborated with prominent actors supporting OS and since 2023 serves on the CoNOSC Board. From 2019 – 2022, she coordinated the development of the National Strategic Framework for OS in Romania, embodied in the White Paper on the Transition to Open Science 2023-2030. Passionate about the philosophy and sociology of science, Alina obtained her PhD in sociology, in 2020, at the University of Bucharest.

science efforts as the country's central hub, guiding the development and application of open science policies and practices.

Since 2018, UEFISCDI has spearheaded efforts to guide and support Romania's Open Science journey. It established the Open Science Knowledge Hub (OSKH) and led the development of the National Open Science Strategic Framework, which includes the [White Book of the Transition to Open Science](#) and a specific objective within Romania's [National Strategy on Research, Innovation, and Smart Specialisation \(2022–2027\)](#). Furthermore, UEFISCDI's recommendations have been integrated into the National Plan for Research, Development, and Innovation, the primary instrument for implementing these strategic recommendations.

Over the past few years, I have witnessed a remarkable shift in the perception among research stakeholders in Romania. Initially, there was a natural skepticism, mainly due to a lack of understanding and resources to support Open Science initiatives. However, as awareness has grown, we've seen increased interest and participation. Additionally, the global momentum towards Open Science has also influenced the Romanian landscape.

How does the Agency support researchers in the adoption of Open Science?

To support researchers in the transition, UEFISCDI has developed and distributed resources on topics such as open access, citizen science, and FAIR Research Data Management. These materials are accessible through the national [Open Science portal](#). UEFISCDI has also launched an open science community on its [BrainMap](#) platform to enhance collaboration, and organizes regular webinars and events, fostering awareness, best practices, and capacity-building across Romania's research ecosystem.

How does the Agency align and partner with European Initiatives to strengthen Open Science and Research Assessment in Romania?

UEFISCDI's commitment to open science is bolstered by its involvement in several European and international initiatives. It collaborates with organizations such as [Science Europe](#), and UNESCO, mainly through the [UNESCO Chair of Science and Innovation Policies-SNSPA](#), [COARA](#), [OpenAIRE](#), and the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#), and serves as an observer in the [EOSC Association](#). These collaborations provide UEFISCDI with access to international standards and best practices.

At present, a significant movement towards reforming research assessment is happening, with CoARA as a lead initiative. As an early signer of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), UEFISCDI has actively fostered specific dialogue through workshops and discussions. We believe that practical support in the transition to more holistic assessment methods should be focused on showcasing practices and ongoing work from various countries to demonstrate the tangible benefits of such a reform, while also co-creating tailored tools and guidelines to specific contexts. In line with these, UEFISCDI recently organized an [international conference](#) in Romania dedicated to rethinking research assessment while considering Open Science. The event featured discussions on recent developments and policies, focusing on different perspectives and case studies from practice.

What is next in terms of support for Open Science in Romania?

As a participant in the [OPUS project](#), UEFISCDI is pioneering new requirements and research assessment criteria within a specific funding program, including mandatory Data Management Plans aligned with FAIR

principles for the funded projects - a first for Romania. UEFISCDI is using the **OPUS Research Assessment Framework (RAF)** to pilot these new assessment criteria, allowing it to navigate the challenges of institutional change while adapting to new open science policies. Moreover, in synergy with another European project - **GraspOS** - UEFISCDI is developing and will trial a **new researcher profile**, embedding Open science practices, based on the OPUS RAF.

On another level, UEFISCDI recently started a new project with a specific activity to co-create with researchers (especially ECRs) new recommendations for adapting the national curricula and training programmes to new professional profiles and skills required for Open Science (e.g., data stewards, data technicians, legal experts on rights retention or data security).

Through support for policy making, capacity-building, and practical implementation pilots

(like in the OPUS or GraspOS), UEFISCDI aims to create a research landscape where researchers operate in a more open, collaborative, and innovative scientific environment. For this, it is essential to involve stakeholders directly in the transition reforms. Engaging researchers, policymakers, and university administrators in co-creation processes ensures that the solutions are not only accepted but also effectively implemented.

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